

Chemical Examination of the Fixed Oil from the Seeds of *Strychnos potatorum* "Linn.F."

I. Mixed Fatty Acids

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STRYCHNOS POTATORUM "Linn. F" (Hindi—'Nirmali') is a plant which belongs to the family of *Loganiaceae*. This plant is found in Deccan peninsula extending north west to Sone river. The seeds of this plant are of great medicinal use^{1,2}. The seeds are useful to lachrymation or copious watering of eyes, in dysentery, diabetes and gonorrhoea.

In the present work the mixed glycerides, separated from the fixed oil, have been characterized by their fatty acid composition. The fatty acids have been prepared by usual method³. The mixed fatty acids (free from non-saponifiable matter) have been fractionated by solid-liquid counter current separation method^{4,5} and the fatty acids of each fraction have been identified by qualitative reversed phase paper partition chromatography⁶ and thin layer chromatography⁷. The unsaturation in mixed fatty acids has been determined by ultraviolet spectrophotometry after alkali-isomerisation⁸.

Palmitic, stearic and arachidic acids have been found to be major saturated components of seed

glycerides of *Strychnos potatorum*, these together with lignoceric acid constitute nearly half of the total fatty acids. Stearic and arachidic acids are present almost in equal quantities. The unsaturated components are oleic and linoleic acids.

Experimental

The oil (yield 5.4%), extracted from dried seed powder in a soxhlet with petroleum ether (40°-60°) was fractionated into glycerides and phospholipids by the use of anhydrous acetone in which the latter is insoluble when taken up with 10-15 times its volume of acetone and kept at 0° in a refrigerator for 2-3 days. The mixed glyceride was found to be having the following constants: moisture, 2.1%, specific gravity (d_{25}^{25}), 0.9, refractive index (n_D^{25}), 1.4970, viscosity (η) 3.8 (at 30°), saponification value, 151.7, iodine value, 53.4 and acid value, 6.9. The mixed fatty acids were found to have the neutralization value, 196.1 and iodine value, 71.4. The non-saponifiable matter was 5.3%.

1. Solid-liquid counter current separation :

For the separation of fatty acids from their mixture, solid liquid counter current separation technique was adopted. The fatty acids were distributed into a mixture of two or three as their urea adducts. The solvent system consisted of a saturated solution of urea in methanol-ethyl acetate (7:3) solvent. The solvent, decanted from each fraction was collected in a flask and it constituted the raffinate fraction. The fatty acids from the adducts and raffinate were regenerated by the use of acidulated water followed by their extraction with ether. The dried fatty acids were collected from each fraction and their

TABLE I—SOLID-LIQUID COUNTER CURRENT SEPARATION OF MIXED FATTY ACIDS

Fraction No.	Weight g	Neutralization value	Iodine value	Component fatty acids					
				Palmitic	Stearic	Arachidic	Lignoceric	Oleic	Linoleic
1.	1.59	180.4	18.0	—	0.65	—	0.62	0.32	—
2.	1.22	190.6	38.9	—	0.14	0.55	—	0.53	—
3.	0.89	186.4	59.3	—	—	0.60	—	—	0.29
4.	1.11	192.0	76.2	—	—	—	0.17	0.94	—
5.	1.15	196.3	102.4	—	0.34	0.16	—	—	0.65
6.	0.61	198.6	110.4	—	0.21	0.03	—	0.37	—
7.	0.71	210.9	82.3	0.06	—	—	—	0.65	—
8.	0.58	201.5	79.2	0.07	—	—	—	0.51	—
Raffinate	1.39	208.5	108.4	0.63	—	—	—	0.60	0.16
Total	9.25			0.76	1.34	1.34	0.79	3.92	1.10
		% Fatty Acids		8.2	14.5	14.5	8.5	42.4	11.9
		% Mole		9.3	14.7	13.5	6.7	43.5	12.3

iodine and neutralization values were determined to calculate the amount of fatty acids present in each fraction.

TABLE 2—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC OBSERVATIONS

Wavelength (nm)	Before isomerisation ^a		After isomerisation ^b	
	Absorbance	$E_{1\%}^{1\text{cm}}$	Absorbance	$E_{1\%}^{1\text{cm}}$
233	0.052	16.083	0.260	105.790
262	0.039	11.987	2.257	104.620
268	0.038	11.929	0.123	50.100
274	0.033	10.225	0.064	26.091

a. Concentration 0.003256 g/100 ml cyclohexane

b. Concentration 0.0024576 g/100 ml ethanol.

Identification of fatty acids :

The fatty acids of each fraction were identified with the help of reversed phase paper partition chromatography and thin layer chromatography.

(a) Revised phase paper partition chromatography :

Whatman No. 1 chromatographic paper impregnated with liquid paraffin (10% solution in benzene) was used. The liquid paraffin constituted the stationary phase. The mobile phase was constituted by paraffin-acetic acid (90%, V/V) system. Chloroform solution of fatty acids was applied to the paper. The paper was developed at room temperature for 10–12 hr. The spots were revealed by dipping the developed paper into a 10% aqueous solution of copper acetate, followed by washing with dilute acid (0.2 ml of acetic acid/litre), drying and immersing for 30 sec in 0.03% (W/V) dithio-oxamide in ethanol. The individual fatty acids were identified by running the standard sample of fatty acids simultaneously.

TABLE 3

Fatty acids	Solid liquid counter current separation method		Spectropho- metric method
	% Fatty acids	Mole %	% Fatty acids
Palmitic	8.2	9.3	
Stearic	14.5	14.7	
Arachidic	14.5	13.5	90.1
Lignoceric	8.5	6.7	
Oleic	42.4	43.5	
Linoleic	11.9	12.3	9.9

(b) Thin layer chromatography :

For thin layer chromatography, silica gel G layer on glass plates, impregnated with 5% solution of liquid paraffin in petroleum ether (40°–60°) was used. The fatty acid fractions were spotted along with reference acids. The plates were developed with acetic acid-acetonitrile (1 : 1) saturated with liquid paraffin. After developing the plates the spots were detected by spraying 1.5% aqueous solution of phosphomolybdic acid.

2. Spectrophotometric analysis of unsaturated acids :

The quantitative analysis of the unsaturated fatty acids was done by subjecting a known weight of fatty acids to alkali-isomerisation using a 6.6% potassium hydroxide solution in ethylene glycol at 180°. A blank experiment was run simultaneously. After dilution with ethanol, the mixture was estimated for conjugated polyene absorption against a blank at required wavelength. For conjugated fatty acids, absorption was directly measured at required wavelength without isomerisation using cyclohexane as solvent. Since the method is an empirical one⁹ the standard values measured on pure acids under identical conditions were used for calculation.

Non-saponifiable matter :

Ethereal solution of non-saponifiable matter on purification through animal charcoal and repeated crystallisation from methanol gave white flakes, m.p. 136°. This compound gave colour reactions of sterols. This product was identified as β -sitosterol as confirmed by its acetate (m.p. 126°–127°), benzoate (m.p. 143°–144°), digitonide (m.p. 221° decomposed) and i.r. spectra.

References

1. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, 'Indian Medicinal Plants', Lalit Mohan Basu, Publishers, Allahabad, Vol. III, 1935, p. 1647.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, 'Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants'. C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 236.
3. T. P. HILDITCH and P. N. WILLIAMS, 'Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats', Chapman & Hall, London, 4th Ed., 1964, p. 678.
4. W. N. SUMMERWELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 3411.
5. R. D. TIWARI, K. C. SRIVASTAVA, S. SHUKLA and R. K. BAJPAI, *Planta Medica*, 1967, **15**, 240.
6. P. E. BALLANCE and W. M. L. CROMBIE, *Biochem. J.*, 1958, **60**, 632.
7. H. P. KAUFMANN and Z. MAKUS, *Fette Seifen Anstrichm.*, 1960, **62**, 1014.
8. J. H. MITCHELL, H. R. KRAYBILL and F. P. ZSCHEILE, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1943, **15**, 1.
9. W. MONTAG, E. KLENK, H. HAYES and R. T. HOJMAN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1957, **53**, 277.